

Validation of a monthly quasi-steady-state simulation model for the energy use in buildings

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Abstract— The evaluation of the energy consumption or the energy performance of buildings, from a complex engineering system point of view, is a multi-parametric problem where different static or dynamic methods are being used. Quantitative analysis is usually required, not only in the context of building regulations, but also as an important engineering tool for planning energy efficiency measures or interventions. In this paper a quasi-steady state model for the energy use in buildings is presented, which combines simplicity, minimum requirements for data input and adequate accuracy. This model is based on the methodologies described in the ISO 13790 standard. It combines a basic steady state physical model, where dynamic effects are also taken into account by introducing different correlation factors and reference parameters. It's main advantage over more complex dynamic models requiring detailed data and high expertise, is that it can be used not only from a small number of experts but also from engineers involved in energy management or energy efficiency projects. This model is validated according to the procedures of the EN 15265 standard, in order to investigate the dependence of the results on the different parameters used.

Keywords—*Modeling of energy use; building energy consumption modeling tools; quasi-steady-state energy simulation model; energy performance of buildings*

I. INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, the global contribution from buildings towards energy consumption has steadily increased up to 40% in developed countries and has exceeded other major energy consuming sectors such as the industrial or transportation sector [1,2,3]. The prospective growth of population will further increase the demand for building services in the future, maintaining an upward trend in energy demand. This is why the energy efficiency in buildings is today a prime objective for energy policy at national and international levels. Since buildings are a large and growing market for energy efficiency, global energy efficiency investment in buildings is projected to increase over 125 billion USD by 2020, driven in part by expanding efficiency-targeted policies [3]. Under this framework, different national or international actions have been undertaken in order to motivate the adoption of energy efficient practices and techniques in the buildings sector, like the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) in Europe [4,5]. From the engineering point of view, buildings, especially in the case of large blocks (commercial, offices, hospitals etc), are in fact complex engineering systems, where a large number of different parameters affects their operation and, consequently, their energy demands. Different calculation methods have been proposed to assess the energy needs of buildings, which are fully described in a set of European or other national or international standards [6]. A compulsory single calculation method for regulation compliance could not have been chosen, due to the limitations and complications that would arise on the market. On the other hand, the variety of existing methods and models usually lead to different results, so the adopted methodologies by the standards should be characterized by certain quality aspects as transparency, robustness and reproducibility. However, for the purposes of real energy saving practice, a balance between accuracy and ease of use should be achieved. For example, dynamic methods generate the most accurate results, but they are introducing a high level of complexity due to the dynamic, non linear and interactive phenomena that should be considered by them, while they are also very demanding in data inputs [7]. For these reasons, they can only be used by a limited number of experts. On the contrary, steady state methods have the advantages of high computation speed and simplification in modeling due to ignoring of dynamic characteristics, which makes them easier to use, with the cost of lower accuracy [7]. A good compromise between the aforementioned methodologies is the quasi-steady-state approach which is described in the EN ISO 13790:2008 international standard [8,9]. This approach is referring to the assessment of the energy needs for heating and cooling, which account for the most important part of energy consumption.

This paper presents an energy calculation model based on the EN ISO 13790:2008 quasi steady state methodology, where all energy calculations are made in a monthly time step, by using monthly average values of input parameters such as temperature,

solar irradiance etc. The analysis results are also given on a monthly basis throughout the year. This method is based on a steady state physical model to calculate heating and cooling demands, where the dynamic effects are also taken into account by introducing certain parameters and utilization factors for both heating and cooling calculations. The calculation model has been implemented in Matlab code and has been validated according to the procedures described in the EN 15265 standard, by examining twelve different test cases [10]. It is shown that the model results are in satisfactory agreement with the reference results provided in this standard. In addition, the dependence of the model results on critical input parameters is investigated.

II. THE QUASI-STEADY-STATE MONTHLY MODEL

A. Basic equations

The energy need for heating or cooling is defined as the heat to be added or extracted from a building in order to maintain certain internal comfort conditions in terms of a desired temperature set-point for heating and cooling modes respectively, while at the same time maintaining the required indoor air quality. According to the quasi-steady-state model of EN ISO 13790, the energy need for heating and cooling is estimated separately for each time-step (a month in the selected monthly model) and each building zone. The analysis is based on a monthly balance between heat gains and heat losses, determined in steady state conditions, where dynamic effects are also taken into account by introducing utilization factors [9].

The energy need for space heating is calculated by the equation [8,9] :

$$Q_H(t) = [(H_{tr} + H_{ve})(\vartheta_{i,set(H)} - \theta_e) - n_{H,gn}(Q_{int} + Q_{sol})]t \quad (1)$$

The energy need for space cooling is calculated as [8,9]:

$$Q_C(t) = [(Q_{int} + Q_{sol}) - n_{C,ls}(H_{tr} + H_{ve})(\vartheta_{i,set(C)} - \theta_e)]t \quad (2)$$

In (1) and (2) H_{tr} and H_{ve} are the heat transfer coefficients of the building due to transmission and ventilation in (W/K), $\vartheta_{i,set(H)}$ and $\vartheta_{i,set(C)}$ are the internal set point temperatures for heating and cooling in °C, ϑ_e is the average monthly temperature of the external environment in °C, Q_{int} are the internal heat gains in MJ and Q_{sol} are the solar gains in MJ. Two utilization factors are introduced, namely $n_{H,gn}$, the dimensionless utilization factor for heat gains in heating mode and $n_{C,ls}$, the dimensionless utilization factor for heat losses in cooling mode. According to the EN ISO 13790 standard, the monthly time step t is given in Ms according to table I, so that the energy needs $Q_H(t)$ and $Q_C(t)$ are given in MJ.

TABLE I. TIME STEP DURATION

Month	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
t (Ms)	2.678	2.419	2.678	2.592	2.678	2.592	2.678	2.678	2.592	2.678	2.592	2.678

B. Dimensionless utilization factors

The dimensionless utilization factor $n_{H,gn}$ for the heating mode takes account of the fact that only a part of the total heat gains (internal and solar) is utilized to decrease the energy needs for heating. The remaining part of the heat gains is in fact increasing the internal temperature above the set point temperature $\vartheta_{i,set(H)}$, causing overheating. So the gain utilization factor $n_{H,gn}$ is a measure of the amount of overheating. Similarly, in the cooling mode the utilization factor for losses $n_{C,ls}$ takes account of the fact that only a part of the total heat transfer (due to transmission and ventilation) is used to decrease the needs for cooling. The remaining part occurs during periods when there is no actual effect on the cooling needs (e.g. nights). The utilization factors are used in the quantitative analysis in order to prevent overestimation of the heating or cooling needs.

The quantitative definitions for the dimensionless utilization factors are based on the so called "heat balance ratio". The heat balance ratio γ_H for heating, or γ_C for cooling, is given for each time step (month) by [8,9]:

$$\gamma_H = \frac{Q_{H,gn}}{Q_{H,ht}} \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma_c = \frac{Q_{c,gn}}{Q_{c,ht}} \quad (4)$$

In (3) and (4) $Q_{H,gn}$, $Q_{C,gn}$ are the total heat gains (internal plus solar) for the heating or cooling mode and $Q_{H,ht}$, $Q_{C,ht}$ are the total heat transfers due to transmission and ventilation for the heating or cooling mode respectively.

The dimensionless gain utilization factor for heating is given by [8,9]:

$$n_{H,gn} = \begin{cases} \frac{1 - \gamma_H^{\alpha_H}}{1 - \gamma_H^{\alpha_H+1}}, & \gamma_H > 0 \wedge \gamma_H \neq 1 \\ \frac{\alpha^H}{\alpha^H + 1}, & \gamma_H = 1 \\ \frac{1}{\gamma_H}, & \gamma_H < 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

For heating mode, γ_H is practically representing the actual gain/loss ratio which is the part of the heat gains that contribute to the reduction of heat demand.

Similarly, the dimensionless loss utilization factor for cooling is given by [8,9]:

$$n_{C,ls} = \begin{cases} \frac{1 - \gamma_C^{-\alpha_C}}{1 - \gamma_C^{-(\alpha_C+1)}}, & \gamma_C > 0 \wedge \gamma_C \neq 1 \\ \frac{\alpha^C}{\alpha^C + 1}, & \gamma_C = 1 \\ 1, & \gamma_C < 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

For cooling mode, γ_C is representing the actual loss/gain ratio, which is the part of the heat losses that contribute in the reduction of the cooling demand. It must be noted that heat transfer $Q_{C,ht}$ in (4) is actually representing gains for the cooling system, since it decreases the interior temperature, thus reducing the cooling load.

In (5) and (6) α_H and α_C are dimensionless parameters defined as:

$$\alpha_H = \alpha_{H,0} + \frac{\tau}{\tau_{H,0}} \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha_C = \alpha_{C,0} + \frac{\tau}{\tau_{C,0}} \quad (8)$$

In (7) and (8), τ is the time constant of the building which is given in hours (h). Practically, the time constant indicates how high or low the thermal inertia of the building structure is, which has a high impact on energy consumption [11,12]. The time constant of the building is estimated by the equation:

$$\tau = \frac{C_m / 3600}{H_{tr} + H_{ve}} \quad (9)$$

where C_m is the internal heat capacity of the building zone in (J/K).

The dimensionless reference numerical parameters $\alpha_{H,0}$ and $\alpha_{C,0}$ and the reference time constants $\tau_{H,0}$ and $\tau_{C,0}$ expressed in hours (h) are defined empirically, so that they can be adjusted at national level. However, there are some reference values for the monthly method given in table II, according to the suggestions of EN ISO 13790.

C. Intermittency

Intermittency is treated in different ways, depending on the specific conditions of each case. When the conditions of table III apply (modes A or B), then intermittent heating and/or cooling are considered as continuous with adjusted set-point temperatures. These adjusted set-point temperatures are then used in equations (1) and (2) for the estimation of the energy needs. Otherwise, the estimations are performed by assuming continuous heating and/or cooling and then a dimensionless

reduction factor for intermittency is applied [8]. In the latter case, the dimensionless reduction factors for heating and cooling modes, $\alpha_{H,red}$ and $\alpha_{C,red}$ respectively, are given by (10) and (11):

$$\alpha_{H,red} = 1 - 3 \left(\frac{\tau_{H,0}}{\tau} \right) \gamma_H (1 - f_{H,hr}) \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha_{C,red} = 1 - 3 \left(\frac{\tau_{C,0}}{\tau} \right) \gamma_C (1 - f_{C,day}) \quad (11)$$

where $f_{H,hr}$ is the fraction of the hours of the week with a normal heating set-point and $f_{C,day}$ is the fraction of the number of days in the week with a normal cooling set-point. By the term “normal” in the preceding definitions is denoted a situation with no reduced set-point or switch-off setting.

III. VALIDATION TEST CASES AND PROCEDURES

The proposed quasi-steady-state model has been validated for both heating and cooling modes by using the procedures described in the EN 15265 standard [10]. This standard is widely used in regulatory context, since it supports the essential requirements of EPBD. It does not impose any particular methodology for energy calculations but there are some fixed basic assumptions to be used. Although this standard is mainly applied for dynamic methods where the

TABLE II. VALUES OF THE REFERENCE PARAMETERS IN (7) AND (8)

Heating Mode		Cooling Mode	
$\alpha_{H,0}$	$\tau_{H,0}$ (h)	$\alpha_{H,0}$	$\tau_{H,0}$ (h)
1	15	1	15

TABLE III. CONDITIONS FOR INTERMITTENCY MODES A AND B

Mode	A	B
Conditions	Set-point temperature variations between normal and reduced setting less than 3 K and/or The time constant of the building $\tau < 0.2 \times$ the shortest reduced setting	The time constant of the building $\tau > 3 \times$ the longest reduced setting
Set-point temperature selection	The time average of set-point temperatures	The set-point temperature for normal heating/cooling

time step of the analysis is very small (e.g. an hour or less) compared with the monthly model presented in this paper, it has been chosen as a good reference for validation results.

The validation procedures concern the evaluation of heating and cooling energy needs for 12 different case studies referring to a single zone office room, shown in fig. 1, with fixed thermal and physical properties for each case. The case studies are obtained by using different combinations of transparent (glazed) elements, opaque elements (walls, ceiling/roof, floor), internal gains and heating/cooling system operation according to table IV.

Fig. 1. Test room with a glazed element facing west

TABLE IV. CHARACTERISTICS OF TEST CASES ACCORDING TO EN 15265

Test case	Glazing	Ceiling/Floor	Internal Gains	Operation
No.1	Shaded	Type 4, Adiabatic	20 W/m ²	Continuous
No.2	Shaded	Type 3*, Adiabatic	20 W/m ²	Continuous
No.3	Shaded	Type 4, Adiabatic	0	Continuous
No.4	Unshaded	Type 4, Adiabatic	20 W/m ²	Continuous
No.5	Shaded	Type 4, Adiabatic	20 W/m ²	10 h/day,
No.6	Shaded	Type 3*, Adiabatic	20 W/m ²	10 h/day,
No.7	Shaded	Type 4, Adiabatic	0	10 h/day,
No.8	Unshaded	Type 4, Adiabatic	20 W/m ²	10 h/day,
No.9	Shaded	Type 5* External Roof	20 W/m ²	10 h/day, Weekdays
No.10	Shaded	Type 4 External Roof	20 W/m ²	10 h/day, Weekdays
No.11	Shaded	Type 5* External Roof	0	10 h/day, Weekdays
No.12	Unshaded	Type 5* External Roof	20 W/m ²	10 h/day, Weekdays

* Type 3 ceiling elements and type 5 roofs are characterized by higher mass, i.e. higher heat capacity than type 4 ceiling elements.

For the previously described test cases different scenarios have been examined for the calculation of critical parameters, such as the dimensionless parameter α_c in (8) for cooling mode and the estimation of the internal heat capacity of opaque elements which affect C_m in (9). Regarding parameter α_c , two different simulations have been carried out: one by using (8) with the default values of table II for $\alpha_{c,0}$ and $\tau_{c,0}$ reference parameters and a second one based on the formula for α_c proposed by Corrado and Fabrizio [13]:

$$\alpha_c = 8.1 - 13\xi + \frac{\tau}{17} \quad (12)$$

On the other hand, regarding the estimation of the internal heat capacities of opaque elements, different simulations have been made with or without using the corrected values for the surface resistance, according to the simplified calculations described in Annex A of EN ISO 13786 [14].

Furthermore, the model's results for test case No.6 have also been compared with the reference results of EN ISO 13790, Annex J worked example. This example is in fact referring specifically to the application of the monthly method at test case No.6 of EN 15265. Although the test case is identical in both standards, different results are given as reference in the texts of them. On the other hand the results of Annex J are described in more detail, providing not only the total annual energy needs for heating or cooling, but also the energy gains or losses by category (heat transfer, ventilation, internal gains and solar gains) in monthly time steps.

IV. VALIDATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A great number of simulations have been performed for the 12 test cases described in section III, with different assumptions, in order to investigate the impact of the parameters affecting the accuracy of the results, in comparison with the reference figures given in the EN 15265. In all cases, the relative errors have been estimated on an annual basis for the heating or cooling mode respectively, according to (13) and (14):

$$r_{Q,H} = \frac{|Q_H - Q_{H,ref}|}{Q_{H,ref} + Q_{C,ref}} \quad (13)$$

$$r_{Q,C} = \frac{|Q_C - Q_{C,ref}|}{Q_{H,ref} + Q_{C,ref}} \quad (14)$$

where Q_H , Q_C are the estimated annual energy needs in kWh for heating and cooling and $Q_{H,ref}$, $Q_{C,ref}$ are the corresponding reference results given in the standard.

The weather data that have been used throughout the performed simulations are the monthly averages of the hourly values provided in Annex A of EN ISO 15265.

The application of surface resistance correction for the estimation of the internal heat capacities of opaque elements has a direct impact on C_m and, therefore, on the time constant of the building τ , as shown in table V. In general, if correction is applied, then lower C_m and τ values are yielded. The corresponding relative errors $r_{Q,H}$ and $r_{Q,C}$ of the model, by

TABLE V. VALUES OF THE REFERENCE PARAMETERS IN (7) AND (8)

Correction for surface resistance in internal heat capacity	NO		YES	
	C_m (MJ/K)	τ (h)	C_m (MJ/K)	τ (h)
No.1	3.12	36.68	2.32	27.24
No.2	7.02	82.64	4.10	48.24
No.3	3.12	36.68	2.32	27.24
No.4	3.12	31.45	2.32	23.36
No.5	3.12	36.68	2.32	27.24
No.6	7.02	82.64	4.10	48.24
No.7	3.12	36.68	2.32	27.24
No.8	3.12	31.45	2.32	23.36
No.9	7.02	60.44	4.10	35.28
No.10	3.12	30.51	2.32	22.66
No.11	7.02	60.44	4.10	35.28
No.12	2.99	22.93	4.10	31.46

Dependence of relative error $r_{Q,H}$ on surface resistance correction

(a)

Dependence of relative error $r_{Q,C}$ on surface resistance correction

(b)

Fig. 2. Effect of the surface resistance correction in heat capacitance for the 12 test cases of EN 15265. (a) Relative error in annual energy needs for heating. (b) Relative error in the annual energy needs for cooling.

using the values of table V, are given in fig. 2. These results show that the corrected (for the surface resistance) values of the internal heat capacitance and the corresponding reduction in time constant τ , provide higher accuracy in the calculations of the annual heating mode, especially for the test cases No.6 through No.12 where the heating system is operating in intermittent mode, i.e. 10 hours/day during weekdays, while in weekends the system is off (table IV). The only exception is case No.8 where the correction increases the error, but this is of minor importance since the error is kept low anyway. On the contrary, the correction seems to give worse results for cooling mode in most cases, although cooling mode yields in general lower errors than the heating mode. The observed differences can be attributed to the dependence of utilization factors $n_{H,gn}$ and $n_{C,ls}$ on τ , according to (5), (6), (7) and (8). Also, the reduction factors $\alpha_{H,red}$ and $\alpha_{C,red}$ for intermittency are affected by τ , as shown by (10) and (11). It should be noted that all the previous estimations were made by applying (7) and (8) and by using the reference parameters of table II.

The next step was to investigate the impact of the application of formula (12) for the dimensionless parameter α_c in cooling calculations. The generated errors are shown in fig. 3 in comparison with the errors of fig. 2(b) for the corrected internal heat capacitance. It becomes clear that (12) is providing improved results for cooling mode calculations, due to the lower relative errors in the annual cooling energy needs. It must be noted that the heating calculations are not affected in any way by the application of (12), so the relative error $r_{Q,H}$ (corrected) in fig. 2(a) applies also in this case.

In conclusion, by combining the corrected (including surface resistance) heat capacitance values for the estimations of C_m and τ , which provides lower errors for heating mode, and by applying formula (12) for α_c in cooling mode, the proposed model has been properly adjusted to give satisfactory accuracy according to the test cases of EN 15265. The final results of the proposed model for the annual energy needs for heating and cooling, along with the reference results according to EN 15265, are given in figure 4. It becomes clear that the model generates a good match to the reference values, i.e. with relative errors not greater than 15%, in all cases, with the exception of test case No.11, where the relative error in heating mode is marginally higher, at 16%.

The effect of alternative calculation for α_c

Fig. 3. Relative error in the estimation of the annual energy needs for cooling, by applying (12) for dimensionless parameter α_c .

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Model results for the annual energy needs for (a) Q_H for heating and (b) Q_C for cooling, compared to the reference results for the 12 test cases of EN 15265.

Overall, the graphs of fig. 4 show a general trend concerning the monthly quasi-steady-state method to provide results somehow higher than other more accurate but complex dynamic methods [15].

The proposed model has also been tested on the test case described in Annex J of EN 13790, which is in fact the test case No. 6 of EN 15265, with the important difference that the reference data are provided in higher detail, namely on monthly basis rather than the annual basis used in EN 15265. Hence, the model's behaviour in intermediate periods of the year could be evaluated. The results show a very good match between the model's results and the reference values, with very low relative errors, as indicated in table VI.

TABLE VI. RELATIVE ERRORS FROM THE MODEL'S APPLICATION ON THE WORKED EXAMPLE OF EN 13790-ANNEX J.

Month	$r_{Q,H}$	$r_{Q,C}$	Month	$r_{Q,H}$	$r_{Q,C}$
Jan.	0.01	0.00	Jul.	0.00	0.03
Feb.	0.01	0.00	Aug.	0.00	0.02
Mar.	0.01	0.01	Sep.	0.01	0.01
Apr.	0.03	0.02	Oct.	0.03	0.00
May	0.02	0.03	Nov.	0.01	0.00
Jun.	0.00	0.03	Dec.	0.00	0.00
$r_{Q,H}$ (annual)		0.007	$r_{Q,C}$ (annual)		0.008

Fig. 5. Model results for monthly energy needs for heating, Q_H , or cooling, Q_C , for test case No.6, compared with the reference monthly energy needs according to EN ISO 13790, Annex J. The relative error on yearly basis is low, i.e. 0.7% for heating demands and 0.8% for cooling demands.

Furthermore, the estimated monthly heating and cooling needs are shown in fig. 5 with respect to the reference values of EN 13790.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a quasi-steady-state model for the calculation of the energy needs for heating or cooling in buildings. This model simulates the energetic requirements of a building on monthly basis, while dynamic effects due to thermal capacitances and heat gains from solar or internal heat sources are considered through certain correlation factors. The basic advantages of this approach over more complex dynamic methods is the simplicity, the time effectiveness and the minimized requirements for input data, which makes it suitable for engineers working in energy management or energy efficiency projects in buildings. Although the proposed model is based on the ISO EN 13790 standard, certain improvements have been made, such as the implementation of an alternative estimation for dimensionless parameter α_c for the cooling mode and the use of the corrected heat capacitance values, including surface resistances, for the estimation of the time constant of the building. The model has been thoroughly tested and validated by using standard test cases described in the EN 15265 and the ISO EN 13790 (Annex J) technical standards. It must be noted that EN 15265 is normally applied for dynamic models only, which exhibit significantly higher levels of accuracy compared to non-dynamic models as the quasi-steady-state monthly model presented in this work. However, the validation process has shown that the proposed model's results are within satisfactory accuracy limits, which makes it a useful tool for the calculation of energy heating and cooling needs at different building types.

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